

IMPROVING THE MORAL AND MORAL VALUES OF STUDENT GIRLS ON THE BASIS OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF THE TIMURIAN PRINCESSES

Qurbonova Dilafruz Toshturdiyevna

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy of the Faculty of Samarkand State University named after Sharaf Rashidov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6385182>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

Moral, student girls, spiritual heritage, Timurian princesses, development, educating.

ABSTRACT

As our country goes on the path of building a just democratic state, a free civil society, this process raises the upbringing of a harmonious generation in the spirit of humanism to the level of a topical issue. Humanism is an integral part of the spirituality of our nation, the main basis of its national identity. It is a multifaceted concept, which includes such moral and moral features as nation-wide harmony, social and religious tolerance, interaction, nobility, generosity. In this article, ideas and comments on improving the moral and moral values of student girls on the basis of the spiritual heritage of the Timurian princesses are made.

In today's difficult period, it has become an important and responsible task to educate highly spiritual, enlightened young people who correctly understand their national values, national identity, have their own beliefs and understanding. After all, what will be the future of our country depends on the potential and comprehensive maturity of young people.

Undoubtedly, historical memory, culture, Enlightenment, scientific heritage of our great scientists play a decisive role in educating the growing generation as a mature and perfect person in every way. Therefore, in the period of independence, a great deal of work was carried out to study the life and invaluable heritage of our great ancestors, to improve and preserve their pedigree.

Among the women there were enthusiastic rulers, wise advisers, mature

wise men, crucial scholars, smooth speaker poets and clever art critics. In addition, the ruler of the massagetes, the ruler of the ancient Palmyra, Zinovia, the Queen of Spain, Isabella, the Armenian queen Tamara were mature political rulers of their time. Although such a ruler, scientist, poetess and wise women can be counted with a finger in the West, but in the Eastern countries they can meet a lot. Let's list only some of the women and girls belonging to the Temur and temurid dynasty: the wife of the great sahibqiran Amir Temur (1336-1405)-the Palace Mulk lady (1341-1408, Bibikhanim), the wife of Shahruh Mirzo (1377-1447) in Herat — the wife of Gavhar shod Begim (1379-1457)1 Khalil Sultan Mirzo (1384-1411) — the beloved wife of shod Mulk wife (1387-1411), Sultan the wife of Hussein Boygaro (1438-1506) — Khadijah Begim (1451-1511), the eldest

daughter of Omar Sheikh Mirzo (1456-1404) — Khan Begim (1477-1544), daughter of Zahiriddin Muhammad Baburshah (1483-1530 — Gulba Begim (1523-1603), the wife of the Badakhshan ruler Suleyman Mirzo — harem Begim (1514-1589), the beloved wife of the Jahongir King (1569-1627) — Nurjahan Begim (Mehriniso, 1577-1645), the beloved wife of the King Jahon (1592—1666) — classical Mahal (Arjumand Bonu, 1594—1631), the daughter of the King Jahon - Jahon Oro Begim (1614-1681), the daughter of Aavrangzeb Olemgir (1618-1707) — Zebunniso Begim (1639-1702) is one of those sentences. Sahibqiran Amir Temur Malika Sarai estate until the introduction of the lady in his marriage, there were other wives in harem. But the palace belonging to the Khan generation is considered to be the most magnificent of all the princesses in the harem, the estate lady achieves the title of "great lady" or "Bibikhanim". Of course, in order to be a Musharraf to such an honor, intelligence, taste, the greatness of the circle of thought was the main factor.

Also, historical sources testify that the Palace was also in the charming chapter, a highly perceptive, intelligent, entrepreneurial and intelligent owner of the estate lady era. The Palace estate lady was humane, a lover of the motherland, well-aware of the political, social, economic and cultural life of the country, a woman who took part in the affairs of management with wise advice. In particular, with special attention to science and education, the Taliban took care of the sciences. During the military march of Sahibqiran Amir Temur, the Palace estate lady often walked together. According to historical sources unanimously, the very intelligent,

entrepreneurial Palace proprietor actively participated in the ring with his rational advice on some of the problems that arose in the management of the kingdom. Amir Temur Palace although the property is not publicly subject to the lady, but somehow crushed the need in himself to his rational advice. According to the transplants, when Amir Temur begins to march against Iran, Isfahan's blockade extends to much, and the funds to feed the army are missing. Finally, Amir Temur sends an assistant to Samarkand and sends a letter to the Palace estate lady. The letter was short 6 death and said, *"The reserve of the Army is over, send dice from the treasure."* When the Palace estate lady is aware of the contents of the letter, the letter is sent to the back of the "Ulug Amir, if your dice are over, is your policy also over?"- he writes and holds it to the assistant.

On the basis of the spiritual heritage of the timurian princesses, it is important to expand the spiritual and educational worldview of the student girls, as it was mentioned above, in the improvement of the moral and moral values of the student girls. Girls with comprehensive knowledge, potential and spirituality are in fact the future of our true nation. In the person of Amir Temur, we see the most mature spirituality of that time. He was a clever man who knew the history of previous ancestors well, deduced from their mistakes and achievements, applied each of their knowledge to practice. He was a straight, orphan, science-loving, knowledgeable ruler who attained perfection in morality and manners, energetic in faith, struggling for justice, a lover of science, not tired of studying for a lifetime. According to the information, he

pampered the famous scientists of his time with both wisdom and sharp knowledge.

He was a thorough master of religious and secular sciences, and his session was governed by scholars. The owner spent his free time with a game of chess, sharpening the mind, hand-in-hand in preparation for an unexpected blow to his enemies. He created a chess whiteboard, whose grains were multiplied twice for the first time in history.

Under the patronage and leadership of Amir Temur, famous and knowledgeable scholars of that time, Master Builders, religious leaders, healers and representatives of other spheres were invited to Samarkand. Literally, different schools and directions of the Eastern world joined each other, and this factor began new discoveries and innovations of that time.

If we look at those times, we will witness a strong emphasis on science and science. Patronage in science, the construction of large libraries, the collection of famous works of Western and Eastern scientists are also important signs of the period of awakening. Rightfully, the era of Amir Timur and temurids can be considered the second period of awakening in the history of Central Asia.

In raising the spirituality and enlightenment of student girls, indeed, the Queen of Temuri is a comprehensive study. Just as there can be no vacuum void both in nature and in society, emptiness can never be allowed to exist in the field of ideology. In our opinion, the national ideology does not allow such an ideological gap to penetrate into the reach of foreign ideas, enriches spiritual life with high and attractive ideas that are in the interest of the whole people and each citizen. This, in

turn, will strengthen the sense of confidence in Citizens for tomorrow and hope for the future.

It is known that if there is no need for spirituality in society, it will never arise, nor will it develop. The need itself is also determined by the level of spirituality. Striving for spiritual perfection is a virtue associated with the essence of man. The development of spirituality has a positive impact on the development of society and the fullness of the individual. In this regard, the first connoisseurs of spirituality are these female girls. Considering that the student is the future mother of the girls, it becomes clear that their spiritual presence is a topical issue.

Spirituality has a very deep and broad meaning. It is the mind and language that makes man a man and radically distinguishes him from other living beings and sharply distinguishes him from others, the mind and mind, humanity, generosity, compassion, compassion, compassion, faith, kindness, patriotism, honesty, purity, respect for nature, love of literature, art and culture, devotion to national and universal values, the language, history, culture of himself and of other peoples, it covers such wonderful qualities and qualities as respect and appreciation of Customs and traditions.

In conclusion, where there is no spirituality, there will be no progress, neither happiness nor future. It is known that in every society the fate of the future, as in the hands of the descendants of the future, the level of spiritual and cultural perfection of each people, first of all, is seen in the education of young people. These student girls will educate future generations of the nation tomorrow. In this regard, we can give examples of the

morality and their spirituality of the timurian princesses to the perfect student girls. Any civilized state, thinking about its prospects, cares about the fate of the

younger generation, about how its spirituality and culture are formed. After all, spirituality means understanding of national self.

References:

1. Amir Temur Ko'ragoni. Zafar yo'li. T., «Nur», 1992.
2. Amir Temur o'gitlari. T., «Navro'z», 1992.
3. Axmedov B. Sohibqiron Temur (hayoti va ijtimoiy-siyosiy faoliyati). T., 1996.
4. Ibn Arabshoh. Amir Temur tarixi. Ikki jildlik. T., «Mexnat», 1992.
5. Mo'minov I. Amir Temurning O'rta Osiyo tarixida tutgan o'rni va roli. T., «Fan», 1998.